

The Qualitative Measurement towards Organizational Behaviour by using Kano Method, CRM and ServQual

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to study the organizational behavior of the employees by using SERVQUAL and Kano model. The usual application of SERVQUAL and Kano model is to find out the needs of the customer but for this research, it is used to find out the employees needs and feelings towards the organizational. SERVQUAL used to do a gap analysis of an organization's service quality performance against the service quality needs of its customers. The Kano Model classifies product attributes based on how they are perceived by customers and their effect on customer satisfaction. The Kano model defines various product attributes that are considered important to customers and as a decision maker. As result, the attributes that has the biggest factor in the behaviour of the employees are Managers being in the office to guide the employees, Managers helping the employees with the job, All employees able to finish the job on time and Employees respond towards a strict manager. These factors will have a big impact towards the CRM.

Keywords-- Organizational Behaviour, ServQual, Kano, Customer, GAP

I. INTRODUCTION

Firstly, personnel play an enormous function. Such as the dynamics of a small enterprise work surroundings. An effective worker with an amazing mindset, who suggests expert behavior, can assist the enterprise to be triumphant. When personnel are interacting with colleagues, clients and bosses, it is vital that they have strong interpersonal abilities. Being capable of correctly speak, resolve issues and work with others can create a high-quality and green work environment. Employees who display behavioral problems, which includes being anti-social or non-communicative, may be a distraction within the place of job. No longer simplest can this kind of behavior value organization clients, it may also depress the morale of associates, as well. Personnel frequently constitute their agency's image on and rancid the work. The worker moves are reflective of the corporation as a whole. The trends in actual control practice

are, usually, transferring in a direction precisely opposite to what the corporation pursuits to achieve (Covey, 1989). A number of the problems emerged are personnel do no longer observe the guidelines and policies of place of work. Its miles tough to understand the reasons behind those behaviors. The feelings of the personnel are cannot be degree and it is tough to provide an explanation for why they do sure matters. The reason of Organizational Behavior looks at is to recognize those behaviors and the motive why it happens.

What is the value of a satisfied customer? What is the potential cost of an upset consumer? The ones numbers are 'unknown and unknowable' however is seriously crucial. Behnam (2017). He claimed that Sir Deming says that the pleasure of clients is unknowable however it is very essential to recognize their degree of pride. A few researchers absolutely keep away from "satisfaction" as a measurement goal due to the fact it is "too fuzzy a concept to function a significant benchmark." rather, they focus at the client's whole revel in with a company or provider touch and the distinct evaluation of that revel in. So that it will increase the customer delight, personnel desires to serve the client inside the proper way and manner. Customer satisfaction is not the simple element we need to consciousness on. The personnel' emotions also want to take delivery of interest to, as they are those, which might be handling the customers. We aim to apply the approach of SERVQUAL and Kano model to have a look at the behavior of the employees.

Lastly, so as to growth the customers' experience, the carrier excellent of the personnel desires to be expanded. If you do not cope with the personnel, they cannot contend with the customers (Cooney, 2005). Personnel wishes to be saved satisfied to maximize their capability. Unhappy employees have an effect on their overall performance and consequently will have an effect on the clients enjoy. To get a high client satisfaction, the personnel needs to carry out at their excellent. With the personnel performing at their best, the quality of the service can be at the highest level. The personnel come to be part of their business enterprise with

diverse needs and expectations. Extraordinary personnel have exceptional ideals, attitudes, values, backgrounds and thinking. In an employer employee will want to work with each different and the behavior of every worker may affect the others behavior. The organization as a whole will want the personnel to paintings effectively so their ability can be maximized. This have a look at will intention to cause methods a way to boom the first-rate of the organizational behaviors.

II. THEORETICAL APPROACH

2.1 Organizational Behavior

Organizational behavior research the impact people, agencies, and systems have on human behavior inside companies. it is an interdisciplinary location that consists of sociology, psychology, conversation, and control. Organizational behavior enhances organizational principle, which makes a specialty of organizational and intra-organizational subjects, and complements human-resource research, that is extra focused on normal commercial enterprise practices (Robbins et al., 2009). Models are frameworks or feasible reasons why do people behave as they do at work. There are such a lot of models as many as organizations. Various outcomes at some point of the corporations are substantially because of variations within the models of organizational behavior. All of the models are categorised into four types: collegial, supportive, custodial, and autocratic, (Wibowo, 2016). OB is the look at of human behavior in groups. It is also the interface among human behavior and the organization itself.

First, the managerial orientation of Autocratic model is authority. The personnel are more obedient and dependent at the managers. Thus, the orientation of employees toward the managers is obedience. Under autocratic, personnel deliver better overall performance due to their achievement power. It is also, because of their unlicking to the boss or because of a few different things. Managers adopts opportunity and higher approaches to manage human beings at work are suggested with emerging understanding the desires of the workers combined with ever changing social values and norms. This gave genesis to the second kind of models or organizational behavior (Ivanko, 2013).

Second, the basic of custodial model is managerial orientation of money. The workers are orientated in the direction of bonuses and dependence at the organization. The employee need that is met is security. Passive cooperation is the performance result. At the same time studying the personnel, although the personnel do not talk back to their boss when managed under autocratic style, the managers found out and identified that they without a doubt think back about the system. Such personnel packed with frustration let out their anger on their co-workers,

households and neighbors. This makes the boss think other way to increase higher employee satisfaction. The employees are more responsible and self-discipline. Even though the custodian method gives protection and pleasure, it haves its own disadvantages. The employees are not able to achieve the maximum growth they are supposed to achieve. Although the personnel are glad, they are not inspired in doing their work. It has be found that happy workers aren't always maximum productive workers (Ivanko, 2013).

Third, the supportive model is founded on leadership, not on money or authority. In truth, the managerial management style provides surroundings to assist personnel develop and attain their obligations successfully. The managers understand that the workers are not by nature passive and disinterested to organizational needs, however they are made so by an inappropriate leadership style. The managers believe that given due and appropriate modifications, the workers turn out to be prepared to share responsibility, increase a power to make contributions their mite and improve themselves. For this reason, under supportive technique, the control's orientation is to assist the worker's activity overall performance for assembly both organizational and individual desires. However, the supportive model of organizational behavior is discovered more beneficial and effective in evolved nations and less effective in growing international locations like ours due to employee's greater awakening in the former and less one within the latter nations (Ivanko, 2013). Lastly, the collegial model is an extension of the supportive model. Because the literal meaning of the work 'college' approach a collection of humans having the not unusual cause, the collegial model relates to a team work/idea. The simple basis of the collegial model lies on control's building a feeling of partnership with employee. They recall managers as joint contributors to organizational fulfilment in place of as bosses. Its best gain is that the employee becomes self-discipline. Feeling responsible backed via self-discipline creates a sense of crew work similar to what the participants of a football team experience. The studies research file that as compared to standard management model, the extra open, participative, collegial managerial approach produced improved consequences in situations in which it is far appropriate.

As a gap analysis, it can be said that, even though there are four separate models, almost no organization operates exclusively in a single. There will usually be a predominate one, with one or greater areas overlapping in the other models. The first model, autocratic, had its roots inside the industrial revolution. The managers of this kind of organization function out of McGregor's Theory X. The next three models begin to build on McGregor's Theory Y. They have every evolved over a period and there may be no one "best" model (McGregor, 1960). The collegial model must

no longer be idea because the final or best model, but the beginning of a brand-new model or paradigm (Ivanko, 2013).

2.2 Service Quality

Zeithaml, Parasuraman and Berry crated an empiric model, the SERVQUAL Model. The model compares the needs of customer quality and service quality performance. The model are used to analyse gap in the customers needs on service quality against service quality performance of an organization. The model is also call as the GAP model for this reason. It focuses on the perceptions of the customers on the important attributes of service quality. This enables the company to prioritize and focus on the critical attributes to improve their service quality. (Empathy, assurances,

responsiveness, reliability, and tangibility) as mentioned in Table 1 are SERVQUAL model basic dimensions. A set of service attributes that are capable of meeting the expectations of customers and their satisfactions. The dimensions are all important to the clients. Nevertheless, some dimensions are more important than others are. Service provider needs to balance all the dimensions by focusing on the important ones and not ignoring the minor ones. For this reasons, SERVQUAL is a multiple item scale that has a good validity and reliability that can be used to improve service by better understanding consumers perceptions and service expectations. SERVQUAL are designed as a generic measure, can be applied across various types of services (Wisniewski, 2001).

TABLE-I SERQUAL ELEMENTS

DIMENSION	DESCRIPTION
Tangibles	Appearance of physical facilities, equipment, personnel, and communication materials
Reliability	Ability to perform the promised service, dependably and accurately
Responsiveness	Willingness to help customers and provide prompt service
Assurance	Knowledge and courtesy of employees and their ability to convey trust and confidence
Empathy	Caring, individualized attention the firm provides its customers

2.3 Kano Method

In addition to customer loyalty, the major factor to purchasing decision are the quality of services and goods (Kano, 1984). Recently, a range of systems to manage quality has been introduced. It aims to build long-lasting trust with clients and improve customer satisfaction. By conducting surveys, the services and products can be modified to suit the customer preferences. To improve competitiveness and guarantee a good position in the market, the quality of the products are given a high level of attention. Kano Model of Customer Satisfaction categorizes attributes of a product based on their effect on satisfaction of customer and how they are received by the clients. To guide design decisions to determine when more is better and when is good is good enough, these categorizations are useful. In 1980s, a model to make customer satisfactions towards a product or services measurable are developed by Professor Noriaki Kano.

Kano model categorizes client preferences into five group, which are Reverse, Indifferent, Must-Be, One-Dimensional and Attractive. It defines different attributes to a product, which are important to the clients. Most traditional system identify the performance of attributes' importance that the relationship between customer satisfaction and the attributes are linear. Kano model however, categorizes customer satisfaction between customer satisfaction and performance of attributes as non-

linear (Kano et al., 1984, Berger et al. 1993, Matzler et al. 1996, Nilson-Witell and Fundin 2005). In conclusion, this method enables us to identify the key elements of a product or service even though the method requires very high levels of diligence. Besides, needing high experiences, or a questionnaire may seem confusing, it still has a high effect on customer satisfaction (Hankinson, 2005). If customers are dissatisfied or have problems in the product or the services, the method enables us to identify the features that are causing such dissatisfactions. Level of customer satisfaction will rise by determining the defects when it is improved, fixed and developed. The result will be evaluated by Kano mathematical approach (CS-DS).

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Questionnaire Development

It consists of 20 questions that has the attributes of both SERVQUAL and Kano Model. This part alone are divided into the five attributes of SERVQUAL, Tangible, Reliability, Assurance, Responsiveness and Empathy. Each part of the attributes have four Kano attributes, which is Autocratic, Custodial, Supportive, and Collegial. For the functional part, we aim to identify which element effects the most when it is functioning well. The third part of the questionnaire is based on Kano-Dysfunctional questions. It

also consist of 20 questions that has both SERVQUAL and Kano Model attributes, it is also divided to the five attributes of SERVQUAL and each part has the four Kano attributes. In the dysfunctional part, we aim to identify the elements that effects the most it is not functioning well. There are 84 respondents (employees) to be taken as a sample size. Most of the employees are females with about 58% of the worker

in the organization. The average age of the worker are 26-40 years old with almost half of them are married. Majority of the employees here has a degree and diploma certificate. The pay for most of the workers are below than RM 5000. Finally, the employees who work in the organization have work around 1 to 3 years.

TABLE-II SERQUAL ELEMENTS QUESTION

Tangibles	1. Should wear good attire for suitable workplace 2. Physical facilities should be visually appealing 3. Appearance of physical facilities should be in keeping with the type of service 4. Compromise of the facilities with other colleagues
Reliability	5. Should do things by the time they promise 6. Can be rely when given high salary 7. When employees have problems, managers should be rely to guide them 8. Should able to finish their tasks at the time they promise
Responsiveness	9. Good respond to strict type of managers 10. Good respond to bonuses 11. Good respond when managers helps with the task 12. Effective communication among colleagues
Assurance	13. Employees should be able to trust the managers 14. Employees should feel safe to work 15. The employees should be assured with the managers knowledge 16. Employees should be able to trust each other
Empathy	17. Managers should not be too strict with the employees 18. Unrealistic for managers to give very high salaries to employees 19. Managers cannot be expected to give employees personal attention 20. Harmonious teamwork will make employees happy to work

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

First, all the elements need to be identified which element is a Must-be, Attractive, One-dimensional, or Indifferent attributes. Kano questionnaires are to determine how satisfied the customer towards the service, how

satisfied are the employees towards the leadership skills of the managers. The value of each questions CS and DS are tabulated and being rank according to their CS-DS (mathematical approach). The CS-DS with bigger negative value are the attributes that we need to concentrate more on as depicted in Table 3 and Figure 1.

TABLE-III CS DS RANKING

	CS	DS	CS-DS	RANK
1	0.7	-0.4	0.25	14
2	0.6	-0.4	0.2	11
3	0.6	-0.5	0.12	9
4	0.4	-0.4	0	5
5	0.5	-0.5	0.06	6
6	0.3	-0.6	-0.32	1
7	0.5	-0.6	-0.04	3
8	0.4	-0.4	-0.01	4
9	0.5	-0.3	0.25	15
10	0.7	-0.5	0.2	12
11	0.6	-0.3	0.24	13
12	0.6	-0.5	0.1	7
13	0.4	-0.2	0.1	8
14	0.6	-0.3	0.33	16
15	0.4	-0.6	-0.24	2
16	0.7	-0.6	0.13	13

From the comparison of all the functional and dysfunctional of each question, it was found that the attributes for Organizational Behaviour elements are:

- Must-be: Supportive model
- Attractive: Custodial model
- One-dimensional: Collegial model
- Indifferent: Autocratic model

Referring to the ranking in the CS-DS value table, there is a few elements and questions that needs to be

focused on and improved. Based on the ranking, the four top factors that needs to be focused and improved are:

- K7-Managers being in the office to guide the employees
- K19 -Managers helping the employees with the job
- K8-All employees able to finish the job on time
- K9-Employees respond towards a strict manager

Figure1. Kano: CD-DS value

The result shows that the must-be attribute is the supportive model. This means supportive kind of leadership is a Must be element in an organization. Employees feels that managers should help in and guide them to do their job. When the managers does not help them, they feel unhappy because they do not know who to ask if the managers are not in their office. For attractive attributes, it has been found out that custodial model as the most attractive model out of the others. When given bonuses and benefits, the employees feels much more excited to do the job. As for collegial model, the attribute is One-dimensional. Collegial model involves teamwork between the employees. The employees feels that when teamwork is not good, so is the job. When the employees work dynamically, the work produced is much better.

Lastly, autocratic model are found out to be the indifferent attributes. The employees do not care whether the managers are strict or not. As we can see, the must-be attribute is the most important attribute among the others. Without this element, the employees will feel the absentees of these elements. However, when the element is there, they does not feel its presence. The attractive attribute is to attract the employees to do their job. It will improve their performance. As for one-dimensional attribute, it increases as more of the elements is there. When the element is met in a low quantity or quality, the work done will also have the same magnitude. As total result, the K7 and K8 is fall under Must Be category in Kano attributes (Supportive model). In the ServQual analysis, the top four ranked factors need to be focused on and improved as listed in Table 4 below.

TABLE-IV SERVQUAL ATTRIBUTES

Question No	Statement Attributes	ServQual Attributes
K7	Managers being in the office to guide the employees	Reliability
K19	Managers helping the employees with the job	Empathy
K8	All employees able to finish the job on time	Reliability
K9	Employees respond towards a different manager	Responsiveness

It was found that two of the factors are reliability attributes. This shows that the employees feel reliability attribute is important and needs to be improve. They feel they need to rely on their colleague to finish the job on time and to do a perfect job. They also feel that they need to rely on their managers to be in the office so that they can be guided to do the job properly. Empathy also needs focus as the employees feel that when the manager helps them with the job, they will feel happy to do the job. Lastly, the responsiveness attribute also need some focus. Employees will not give a good respond towards a strict manager. They feel like they are controlled in doing their job.

Summarization, this shows reliability is an important attribute. Without that reliability, the employees feel vulnerable in doing their job. They will feel much more secure when the other colleague can be reliable do a good job.

V. CONCLUSION

As a conclusion, to investigate the organizational behavior in a workplace was achieved by using the organizational behavior study on the employees of the workplace to know why they behave the way they did. Organizational behavior study enables us to understand deeply the employee’s feelings towards the organization as a whole. Second, the improvement of customer satisfaction can be studied by using Customer Relationship Management

(CRM), Kano Model and SERVQUAL model. They played as important role as decision maker in constructing the questionnaire and data analysis. By using this method, we are able to obtain the attributes and factors that affect the behavior of the employees towards the organizational. This will allow employers to know which factors to focus on in order to make the employees work at their maximum capacity. The Gap analysis was done towards the Kano Attributes in CRM perspectives such as, the Must-BE attribute (KANO) is a supportive model in CRM. As for SERVQUAL, it is found that the reliability attribute (table 4) needs to be focused on more so that the employees are kept happy. Above all we can say that, the factors of “Managers being in the office to guide the employees” and “All employees able to finish the job on time” are most important factors to be improved. In these reasons, both factors fall under Must Be category and acted as the Supportive Model in CRM.

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